

Mentorship Matters: Investigating the Impact of Mentoring on New Teachers

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Abstract:

The Philippine Educational Sector poses more challenges every time senior teachers leave the institution. In addition, schools need to hire additional teachers to address this issue. In recent years (2011-2019), the number of newly hired teachers increased from 241,000 to 358,000, according to the National Center for Educational Statistics (Digest 2021). With this regard, schools initiated mentorship practices to scaffold the needs of the newly hired teachers. With the help of mentorship, newly hired teachers are equipped with the necessary skills to produce globally competent learners who would be future-ready. In the study of (Schwan, Anna, et al., 2020), newly hired teachers mentored by mentor teachers benefit from positive interactions, collaboration, improved instruction, and a developed sense of community.

Keywords: Mentoring, New Teachers, Challenges

Introduction:

Aspiring teachers, driven by a commendable desire to make a positive difference in the lives of young people, embark on a path to educate future generations and contribute to a stronger society (Callahan, 2016). However, retaining teachers can be challenging, and school districts must prioritize understanding and minimizing teacher departures (Callahan, 2016). To address this, school leaders are placing a growing emphasis on fostering collaboration among educators and equipping new teachers with the necessary skills to flourish in the classroom (Hunter, 2016). This includes new teacher training programs that prioritize in-depth subject matter knowledge, engaging teaching methods, and establishing clear connections between learning concepts (Yirci, 2017). After all, stepping into a classroom for the first time can be overwhelming for new teachers (Marzano, 2017). To be successful educators, they need well-rounded training encompassing subject matter knowledge, teaching strategies, using technology in education, and understanding diverse learners (Allen, 2013).

Research suggests that new teachers take 3 to 7 years to become highly skilled, yet a significant number, over a third, leave the profession within five years (Long, 2010; Shaw & Newton, 2014). One solution to address this high turnover is mentoring programs. However, according to Starr (2015), these programs can struggle if the goals are unclear on the individual (mentors/mentees) and organizational levels. Furthermore, Hudson (2013) emphasizes the importance of well-informed mentors to guide the new teachers effectively.

Specifically, the time constraints of the mentors and new teachers hinder their ability to engage in meaningful mentoring activities. Heavy workloads and packed schedules leave little room for regular mentoring sessions for effective professional development. Thus, researchers are motivated to explore mentoring experiences.

It is time to move from seeing the first year of teaching as a test to gaining experience. Instead, we should view it as a crucial time to provide new teachers with focused support and guidance on instruction. With dedicated time and professional development, new teachers can develop into successful and highly skilled educators (Boogren, 2015). New teachers face a whirlwind of new experiences in their first year: unfamiliar students, navigating school procedures, and building relationships with colleagues, administrators, and parents, all while developing lesson plans, classroom management strategies, and unique teaching styles

(Marzano, 2017). This qualitative study aims to explore the perception of mentoring of new teachers in CPSU San Carlos on their growth, performance, and students learning.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to explore and determine new teachers' experiences and the impact of mentoring on their performance, learning, and professional growth as they navigate their environment. Specifically, this study would answer the following statements:

1. How does mentoring influence your growth as a new teacher at CPSU San Carlos?
2. How does mentoring influence your performance as a new teacher at CPSU San Carlos?
3. How does mentoring influence student's learning as a new teacher at CPSU San Carlos?

Theoretical Underpinnings

Transformative learning theory, introduced by Jack Mezirow in 1978, provides a valuable framework for understanding how mentoring can facilitate significant growth in new teachers. This theory emphasizes critically examining assumptions and biases, a process that can be powerfully catalyzed through thoughtful mentoring conversations. Mentors can help new teachers question their ingrained beliefs about teaching and learning, encouraging them to reflect on their experiences and develop new, more effective approaches in the classroom. By providing a safe space for exploration and challenge, mentoring can foster transformative learning in new teachers, ultimately leading to a deeper understanding of themselves, their students, and the art of teaching.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the research design, the respondents of the study, the data gathering instrument, the data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

Research Design

A qualitative research design will be used to describe the phenomenon of the new teachers' perceptions of how mentoring influences their growth and performance as a new teacher and their students. Effective research on lived experiences begins with self-reflection. Researchers must examine their own biases and experiences related to the topic before delving into case studies of the phenomenon itself (Merriam, 2009). This self-awareness strengthens the case study method, a valuable tool for understanding simple and complex phenomena (Yin, 2014). The case study method, as described by Merriam & Tisdell (2016), proved valuable for enhancing understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

Participants of the Study

The study participants were new teachers in the Central Philippines State University-San Carlos Campus and were interviewed based on the criteria a.) below 3 years; b.) must be full-time in status. According to Creswell (2013), several guidelines for selecting research participants in qualitative research must be met; the first is to seek out individuals who have firsthand knowledge of the phenomenon under investigation. Secondly, participants must be able to describe their observations, interpretations, and feelings about the phenomenon in detail. Thirdly, a diverse range of backgrounds and experiences is required within the group. Finally, Creswell emphasizes the importance of research participants being available for interviews and capable of providing comprehensive, self-reflective responses (Creswell, 2013).

Table 1. Profile of New Teachers in the Central Philippines University – San Carlos

Pseudonym	Sex	Age	Civil Status	Highest Educational Achievement	Years Teaching	College / Department
Dinagra	Male	26	Single	With MA Units	2 years and 6 months	CS
Ninhaya	Male	29	Single	With MA Units	1 year and 4 months	CCS
Daegaba	Female	26	Single	With MA Units	2 years and 9 months	CBM
Annballi	Female	31	Married	With MA Units	2 years and 9 months	CBM
Reapola	Female	27	Single	With MA Units	3 years and 6 months	CCJE
Dhabeci	Female	25	Single	With MA Units	3 months	CCJE
Rafvill	Male	25	Single	With MA Units	1 year	CAF

Earrami	Male		Single	With MA Units	1 year and 8 months	CAF
Zenzapa	Female	34	Married	With MA Units	8 months	COTED
Merogha	Female	25	Single	With MA Units	1 year and 3 months	COTED
Clarami	Female	26	Single	With MA Units	1 year and 1 month	COTED
Gelcano	Female	31	Single	College Graduate	8 months	COTED
Glemano	Male	33	Married	With MA Units	1 year and 4 months	COTED
Edrodri	Male	25	Single	College Graduate	4 months	COTED
Checlar	Female	29	Single	College Graduate	1 year and 4 months	COTED
Flocabra	Female	32	Single	With MA Units	8 months	COTED

Research Instrument

The researchers used purposive sampling in which the participants in this study will be based on the criteria stated. This sample allowed the researchers to learn about a specific phenomenon (Merriam, 2009). Deep interviews and note-taking are done to supplement the study. Also, a semi-structured interview allowing a discussion with the interviewee rather than a straightforward question-and-answer format is done. It contains both open-ended and closed-ended questions. The content validity of the constructed interview questions was subjected to the research experts. To ensure data accuracy, the researcher remains objective while collecting and analyzing data.

This approach allows the researcher to make meaning of the data while minimizing the possibility of introducing their own biases (Merriam, 2009). Beginning with the distribution of family background and age questionnaires to informants, a comprehensive data collection strategy was employed for the study. Before the interviews, participants were given an interview guide outlining the study's objectives and key questions. Field notes were taken throughout the various phases of the study, from the initial contact with conversation partners to the series of interviews conducted, to ensure an accurate and exhaustive data set. The participant's facial expressions, gestures, annotations, emphasis, pauses, and silence were observed and recorded in the field notes during these sessions.

In qualitative research, validity and reliability are not commonly used terms, but rather concepts of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Guest, Namey, & Mitchell, 2021). These terms are collectively known as "trustworthiness," which reflects the idea that qualitative researchers aim to establish confidence in their findings (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Guest et al., 2021). To achieve trustworthiness, qualitative researchers use a range of techniques, such as member checking, thick description, and triangulation, to enhance the rigor and transparency of their studies (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Guest et al., 2021).

According to Creswell and Creswell (2021), trustworthiness is established through several strategies such as prolonged engagement, peer review, member checking, and triangulation. Prolonged engagement refers to the researchers' extended involvement with the research participants to ensure a deep understanding of the study phenomenon. Peer review is the process of having other researchers review the research design and findings to ensure that they are trustworthy. Member checking involves going back to the research participants to validate the findings. Triangulation refers to the use of multiple data sources, methods, and researchers to ensure that the findings are reliable. Other scholars, such as Tracy (2020), have emphasized the importance of reflexivity in establishing trustworthiness in qualitative research. Reflexivity involves acknowledging and reflecting on the researcher's biases, values, and assumptions that may impact the research process and findings. Additionally, Tracy (2020) suggests that researchers should be transparent about their research process and provide a detailed description of their methods, data collection, and analysis to ensure trustworthiness.

Validity of the Research Instrument

The interview questionnaire is validated using Lawshe's validity tool and five jurors who were experts in the field of curriculum and instruction, and it came up that the interview questions were essential and ready to be interviewed and asked by the participants of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

In this study, the researchers asked permission from the Office Campus Administrator, Central Philippines State University-San Carlos Campus to conduct on the targeted participants. After acquiring the needed data,

themes were created, and integration of sub-categories through constant comparison, modification, and analysis of concepts.

To ensure ethical considerations of the research, all participants were informed about the details of the study. Participation in this study is voluntary and they can withdraw anytime without any consequences. They were informed about the academic purpose of the study. The researchers guaranteed the secrecy of the participants by assigning encrypted codes. Confidentiality was ensured as only the researchers had access to the research data.

Thematic analysis is a research method that involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns or themes within data. To carry out this method, the researcher can follow the six phases outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006), which include transcribing the data, reading and re-reading the data, coding the essential features of the data systematically, collating data relevant to each code, collating codes into potential themes, generating a thematic map of the analysis, generating clear definitions and names for each item, and producing a scholarly report of the analysis. For this study, the appropriate technique for data collection was in-depth interviews, which have become the primary data collection method closely associated with qualitative, human scientific research.

Data Analysis

Yin (2014) defines data analysis as the process of examining, organizing, summarizing, and potentially testing evidence to generate findings based on observation and experience. Therefore, the organization of the data will occur throughout the data collection phase and include the review and transcription of interviews as well as the organization of questionnaire data. The goal was to take descriptive and reflective notes and code the themes that emerged from the data. Coding is a researcher-generated method of translating data (Saldaña, 2016).

To analyze the data, the researchers followed Creswell's six steps. Firstly, the transcribed data were organized and prepared. Secondly, the researchers read and re-read the transcripts to gain an overall understanding of the data, noting down initial ideas and impressions. Thirdly, the researchers developed a set of initial codes based on the data collected and research questions. These codes were developed using a systematic and iterative process. Fourthly, the initial codes were reviewed and sorted into potential themes. The themes were reviewed and refined to ensure they were distinct, coherent, and accurately reflected the data. In the fifth step, the researchers reviewed and defined the themes using a thematic map that visually represented the relationship between the codes and themes. The themes were refined and revised until they accurately reflected the data. Finally, the themes were used to develop a scholarly report of the analysis that included a detailed description of the themes supported by relevant quotes from the transcripts.

The report was reviewed and revised to ensure it accurately reflected the data and answered the research questions. Through this thorough analysis process, the study produced valid and reliable findings that shed light on the experiences and challenges of new teachers and how mentoring helped them familiarize the profession (Macapagong, E. et al., 2023)

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured ethical considerations in the study, starting with obtaining informed consent from all participants and assigning pseudonyms to protect their anonymity. Ethical questions arose, particularly regarding the researchers' position in education and the potential for conflicts of interest. However, no other ethical issues surfaced during the study as all participants joined voluntarily, signed consent forms, and were free to withdraw without penalty at any time.

In conducting a rigorous qualitative study, it is crucial to ensure the veracity and transferability of the data collected. Credibility, as defined by Del Siegle (2019), is achieved when the researcher remains on the research site until data saturation is reached. Transferability, on the other hand, pertains to the accurate description of the research environment and underlying presumptions in terms of generalizability within the specific contexts of the study, as outlined by Dawadi et al. (2021). The study's results may also be applicable in other settings or contexts, according to Dawadi et al. (2021) as cited by Macapagong, E. et al. (2023).

Results and Discussion

Participants Personal Biographies

"Dinagra"

Dinagra is a 26-year-old dedicated to serving in the College of Computer Studies for 2 years and 6 months. Single and has achieved a master's degree with units. He is also known for his commitment and diligence in his role, although he currently does not hold a coordinatorship position in his department.

"Ninhaya"

Ninhaya, a 29-year-old male, is a passionate and hardworking faculty member of the College of Computer Studies. He has made significant contributions despite being in the department for only 1 year and 4 months. Single, holds a master's degree with units but does not currently have a coordinatorship role.

"Daegaba"

Daegaba is 26 years old, and a dedicated educator in the College of Business Management. She has been serving for 2 years and 9 months, earning a monthly salary of 16,000 pesos. Single and holding a master's degree with units, she is committed to her professional growth and excels in her academic responsibilities.

"Annbali"

A 31-year-old faculty member in the College of Business Management. Married, she has been with the institution for 2 years and 9 months. Annarose holds a master's degree in units and is known for her dedication and professionalism.

"Reapola"

Reapola, a 27-year-old single female, is a valued College of Criminal Justice Education member. With 3 years and 6 months of service, she is committed to education and in pursuit of academic excellence, holding a master's degree with units.

"Dhabeci"

Dhabeci, a 25-year-old female, is an enthusiastic and committed educator in the College of Criminal Justice Education. Single, she has served for 3 months and holds a master's degree with units. is dedicated to her students and her profession.

"Rafvill"

Rafvill, a 25-year-old single male, is a dedicated faculty member in the College of Agriculture and Forestry. With 1 year of service, he is committed to professional development and holds a master's degree with units.

"Earrami"

Earrami is a dedicated educator in the College of Agriculture and Forestry. He has been serving for 1 year and 8 months and holds a master's degree with units. He is known for his commitment to education and his professional growth.

"Zenzapa"

At 34 years old, Zenzapa is a dedicated female educator in the College of Teacher Education. Married, she has been with the institution for 8 months. She holds a master's degree with units and is committed to providing quality education to her students.

"Merogha"

Merogha, a 25-year-old single, is a dedicated faculty member in the College of Teacher Education. With 1 year and 3 months of service, she holds a master's degree with units. Holds firm to dedication and professionalism.

"Clarami"

Clarami is a 26-year-old single, serving in the College of Teacher Education. With 1 year and 1 month of service, holds a master's degree with units. She is committed to her students and her profession.

"Gelcano"

Gelcano, a 31-year-old single, is a dedicated educator in the College of Teacher Education. She has been serving for 8 months. She holds a college degree and is known for her commitment to education and professional growth.

"Glemano"

Glemano is a 33-year-old married male serving in the College of Teacher Education. With 1 year and 4 months of service, he holds a master's degree with units. He is dedicated to his profession and his students.

"Edrodri"

Edrodri, a 25-year-old single male, is a committed faculty member in the College of Teacher Education. He holds a college degree and has been serving for 4 months. He is known for his dedication to his students and his professional growth.

"Checlar"

Checlar is a 29-year-old single female serving in the College of Teacher Education. Served 1 year and 4 months of service in the institution and holds a college degree. She is committed to providing quality education and professional excellence.

"Florcabra"

Florcabra, a 32-year-old single female, is a dedicated educator in the College of Teacher Education. She has been serving for 8 months and holds a master's degree with units and is known for her dedication and commitment to education.

Emerging Themes

Mentoring and Growth of New Teachers

The qualitative data gathered from interviews with 15 newly hired teachers reveal a significant impact of mentoring on their professional growth. Mentoring provides a platform for beginner educators to acquire essential teaching skills and pedagogical knowledge. The guidance and support offered by mentors enable new teachers to navigate the complexities of classroom management more effectively. For instance, Dinagra, a male teacher with 2 years and 6 months of teaching experience, emphasized the invaluable role of his mentor in helping him develop strategies for classroom discipline and lesson planning. Additionally, mentoring facilitates transformative learning experiences for new teachers, as they critically examine their assumptions and beliefs about teaching and learning. This aligns with Mezirow's Transformative Learning Theory, which emphasizes the importance of questioning deep-rooted beliefs to stand-in deeper understanding. Through reflective conversations with mentors, new teachers like Ninhaya, who has been teaching for 1 year and 4 months, were able to challenge their defined notions and adopt more effective teaching approaches.

Mentoring and Performance of New Teachers

The analysis also highlights the positive influence of mentoring on the performance of new teachers at CPSU San Carlos. Mentoring provides novice educators with socio-emotional support, which helps buffer against the stress and isolation commonly experienced in the early stages of their careers. This emotional scaffolding not only promotes resilience but also cultivates a sense of belonging in the profession. As an example, Reapola, a female teacher with 3 years and 6 months of teaching experience, emphasized how her mentor's encouragement and support helped her navigate challenges and stay motivated in her role.

Still, mentoring facilitates the integration of new teachers into the school culture and community. Mentors serve as liaisons between beginner educators and the broader educational ecosystem, helping them navigate institutional standards, policies, and expectations. This finding is consistent with previous research that highlights the importance of mentorship in nurturing teacher retention and satisfaction (Shaw & Newton, 2014).

Mentoring and Student Learning Outcomes

While the primary focus of mentoring is on the growth and performance of new teachers, it also has implications for student learning outcomes. The qualitative data suggest that effective mentoring positively influences instructional practices, which, in turn, can enhance student engagement and achievement. By providing new teachers with guidance on lesson planning, classroom management, and assessment strategies, mentors contribute to the creation of favorable learning environments. This finding emphasizes the broader impact of mentoring on the quality of education provision.

Conclusions:

The research revealed compelling evidence that mentorship matters significantly. Through this study, it becomes evident that mentorship plays a pivotal role in the professional development, job satisfaction, and retention of novice educators.

Firstly, mentorship fosters the acquisition of essential teaching skills and pedagogical knowledge. New teachers benefit from the experiential wisdom and guidance of their mentors, this will enable them to navigate the complex routes of classroom management more effectively. Moreover, mentorship provides socio-emotional support to new teachers who buffer against the stress of isolation commonly experienced in the early career stage. This emotional scaffolding not only promotes resilience but also cultivates a sense of belonging in the profession.

Furthermore, mentorship facilitates the integration of new teachers into the school culture and community. Mentors serve as liaisons between the greenhorns and the much broader educational ecosystem, helping them navigate institutional norms, policies, and expectations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers strongly recommend the following:

1. Investment in Mentor Training
Schools should invest in comprehensive training programs for mentors to equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to support novice educators effectively.
2. Structured Mentorship Programs

Mentorship programs should be well-defined and structured, with clear guidelines and expectations for both mentors and mentees. Regular check-ins and feedback mechanisms can ensure the success of mentorship relationships.

3. Emphasis on Social Support

In addition to pedagogical support, mentorship programs should prioritize socio-emotional support for new teachers. Developing a culture of empathy and support within the school community can contribute to teacher well-being.

4. Research-Based Practices

Mentorship programs should be informed by research-based practices and evidence-based strategies. Continuous evaluation and refinement based on feedback and data can ensure the ongoing effectiveness of mentorship initiatives.

Finally, mentorship is essential in the progress of the professional development and welfare of emerging educators. Through the adoption of these suggestions and a focus on the requirements of beginner teachers, educational institutions can cultivate more nurturing and welcoming settings that benefit both educators and learners alike.

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